

Theoretical Study of Azaheterocyclic Systems : Azafluoranthenes

SUKANTA KUMAR PAL and N. K. DAS GUPTA*

Chemistry Department, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235

Manuscript received 27 June 1985, accepted 2 April 1986

The molecules azafluoranthenes have been studied using SCFMO method of Pariser and Parr and Pople modified by Dewar and Harget. The ground state and other properties have been predicted and compared with experimental results where available. The $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra for 1-aza- and 3-aza-fluoranthene predicted by the CI method are in good agreement with experimental results and better than those of Michl.

Fig. 1. Azafluoranthene : (1) 1-aza and (2) 2-aza, (3) 3-aza, (4) 7-aza and (5) 8-aza.

$\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra for a large number of compounds^{2,12}. The values of K for $\beta_{\sigma-\sigma}$ used in the CI procedure was changed from 6.927 to 9.1846 eV (Ref. 12), and for $\beta_{\sigma-N}$ it is 6.9612 eV, same as used in the SCF procedure. With this modification we utilised the SCF procedure to generate the initial vectors, β -integrals and γ -integrals to be used in the CI procedure where all the configurations arising from one-electron excitations involving orbitals obtained in a prior self-consistent field calculation. The calculated $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectral transitions for these molecules have been presented in Table 2 along with the oscillator strength (f), which was obtained from the relation¹³,

$$f = 1.085 \times 10^{-5} \bar{\nu} \mu^2 \quad (4)$$

where, $\bar{\nu}$ is the transition energy in cm^{-1} and μ is the dipole length for the corresponding transition

in \AA . The experimental values are presently available only for 1-aza- and 3-aza-fluoranthenes and they have been included in Table 2. On comparison, it is clear that the present work is in good agreement with the experimental ones, specially the results obtained by CI method which is better than the work of Michl¹⁴ who also used limited configuration interaction.

According to Koopmans' theorem¹⁵, the ionisation potential (IP) can be approximated by the highest occupied orbital energy (ϵ_i). But the predicted value of IP is 1 or 2 eV higher than the experimental value. In case of electron affinity (EA), it can also be approximated by the lowest unoccupied orbital energy (ϵ_j). Here too the predicted value of EA differs from the experimental value of EA by 1 or 2 eV. Hence, a correction

TABLE 2 - $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ SPECTRAL TRANSITIONS, ΔE (eV) AND OSCILLATOR STRENGTH (f) OF AZAFLUORANTHENES (AzaF)

Molecule	Experimental transitions ^a		Present work				Other work ^b	
	ΔE	$\log \epsilon$	CI method		SCF method		ΔE	f
1-AzaF			3.15	0.01			3.17	0.0093
	3.39	3.80	3.40	0.48	3.45	0.09	3.44	0.56
	4.03	3.05	3.92	0.04	3.68	0.70	4.16	0.013
	4.42	4.05	4.33	0.15	4.51	0.62	4.41	0.15
	4.88	3.95	4.98	0.06	4.80	0.25	5.16	0.096
			5.18	0.65	5.12	0.38	5.32	0.37
	5.32	4.40	5.39	1.17	5.28	0.30	5.48	1.3
		(0.084)		(0.169)		(0.157)		
2-AzaF			3.39	0.04			3.38	0.44
			3.48	0.45	3.83	0.65	3.50	0.51
			3.86	0.03	3.86	0.28	4.06	0.024
			4.46	0.26	4.64	0.61	4.57	0.29
			4.88	0.26	4.88	0.57	5.08	0.06
			5.08	0.24	4.96	0.27	5.13	0.13
			5.18	0.30	5.05	0.08	5.26	0.54
		5.39	0.91	5.46	0.29	5.45	0.86	
3-AzaF ^b	3.08	2.22	3.11	0.05			3.15	0.057
	3.53	3.74	3.53	0.35	3.45	0.08	3.60	0.40
	3.86	3.01	3.79	0.18	3.70	0.60	3.91	0.23
	4.40	4.38	4.42	0.20	4.12	0.82	4.51	0.25
	4.84	4.30	5.03	0.30	4.99	0.02	5.13	0.44
	5.02	4.24	5.13	0.15	5.10	0.29	5.23	0.33
	5.41	4.44	5.41	0.89	5.36	0.33	5.38	0.23
6.04	4.56	5.89	0.77	6.03	0.42	5.68	0.78	
		(0.098)		(0.142)		(0.188)		
7-AzaF			3.31	0.01			3.30	0.023
			3.63	0.39	3.82	0.43	3.73	0.45
			3.84	0.08	3.98	0.48	3.94	0.099
			4.34	0.48	4.11	0.37	4.56	0.50
			4.86	0.07	4.80	0.39	5.06	0.0013
			5.00	0.02	5.10	0.43	5.07	0.072
			5.28	0.62	5.19	0.29		
		5.41	1.23	5.61	0.02	5.48	1.3	
		5.86	0.45	5.71	0.24	5.57	0.67	
8-AzaF			3.31	0.10			3.34	0.17
			3.52	0.40	3.70	0.68	3.59	0.42
			3.83	0.08	3.91	0.25	3.94	0.096
			4.46	0.14	4.06	0.55	4.63	0.079
			4.96	0.13	4.81	0.53	5.10	0.20
			5.05	0.002	4.96	0.15	5.15	0.067
			5.23	0.56	5.24	0.22	5.36	0.73
		5.37	1.01	5.40	0.32	5.46	0.92	
		5.78	0.62	5.84	0.24			

^aRef. 13. ^bRef. 14. ^cFor 1-AzaF, Ref. 17; and for 3-AzaF, Ref. 14 and J. MITCHELL, *Thor. Chim Acta*, 1969, 20, 66.

Figures in Parenthesis indicate standard deviation.

term is to be added in both the cases of IP and EA in order to obtain their correct values. The following relation between ionisation potential and highest occupied orbital energy and electron affinity and lowest unoccupied orbital energy are in common use in the literature.

$$IP = -(e_i + C) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{and } EA = -(e_j + D) \quad (6)$$

where, C and D are correction terms. Birss and Dasgupta¹⁶ used a value of C to be 1.88 eV and they predicted the ionisation potential of a large number of aromatic hydrocarbons and heterocyclic systems. The value of D is 1.38 being the difference between the lowest unoccupied orbital

energy and the electron affinity of chrysenes. The predicted values of IP and EA are presented in Table 3 which also contains the calculated value of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$, the half-wave reduction potential from the relation proposed by Birss and Dasgupta¹⁶,

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = -0.833 e_f - 3.46 \quad (7)$$

The theoretical π -dipole moment calculated by us is also included in Table 3. (Experimental values are not presently available).

Heat of atomisation, bond energy and stability: 'Dewar' resonance energy (RE) has been calculated from the relation,

$$RE = \Delta H_a - \Delta H'_a \quad (8)$$

TABLE 3—HEAT OF ATOMISATION (ΔH_a), π -BOND ENERGY ($E_{\pi b}$), RESONANCE ENERGY (RE), IONISATION POTENTIAL (IP), ELECTRON AFFINITY (EA), HALF-WAVE REDUCTION POTENTIAL ($E_{1/2}$) AND π -DIPOLE MOMENT (μ)

Molecule*	ΔH_a eV	$E_{\pi b}$ eV	RE eV	RE/bond	IP eV	EA eV	$E_{1/2}$ V	μ D
1-AzaF	133.368	23.785	2.326	0.1224	7.85	0.99	1.57	1.51
2-AzaF	133.455	23.833	2.413	0.1270	7.79	0.80	1.73	1.35
3-AzaF	133.385	23.800	2.342	0.1233	8.01	1.05	1.52	1.30
7-AzaF	133.419	23.818	2.376	0.1251	7.95	0.76	1.76	1.02
8-AzaF	133.430	23.825	2.387	0.1256	7.81	0.92	1.63	1.62

*AzaF = Azafluoranthene.

where, ΔH_a is the heat of atomisation of the molecule and $\Delta H'_a$ is the heat of atomisation of the molecule when π -electrons are localised. In the absence of experimental value of ΔH_a , it can be estimated from the relation,

$$\Delta H_a = E_{\pi b} + E_{\sigma b} + n_{\sigma-H} E_{\sigma-H} \quad (9)$$

where, $E_{\pi b}$, $E_{\sigma b}$ and $E_{\sigma-H}$ are the π -bond energy, σ -bond energy and C—H bond energy, respectively, and $n_{\sigma-H}$ is the number of C—H bond. The value of $\Delta H'_a$ has been evaluated from the relation,

$$\Delta H_a = n'E_{C-C} + n''E_{C=C} + n_{\sigma-H} E_{\sigma-H} \quad (10)$$

where, n' , n'' , E_{C-C} and $E_{C=C}$ represent the number of C—C bonds, number of C=C bonds, C—C bond energy and C=C bond energy, respectively. The values of $n_{\sigma-H}$ and $E_{\sigma-H}$ are the same as in equation (9). The values of E_{C-H} , E_{C-C} and $E_{C=C}$ are taken from Dewar and Harget^{6,7}. The values of ΔH_a and $E_{\pi b}$, resonance energy and resonance energy per bond (RE/bond) have been included in Table 3. From Table 3 it is clear that the resonance energy of azafluoranthenes are comparable to that of fluoranthene (2.353 eV) and it is expected that they are stable aromatic molecule which they are.

Charge density and bond length: Calculated charge density and bond length have been shown in Fig. 1. For 1-aza-, 2-aza- and 3-aza-fluoranthene, the distribution of charge density on nitrogen and *ortho*, *para* and *meta* carbon atoms resemble that of quinoline and isoquinoline¹⁰. For the other two molecules, the similar situation is also observed.

In case of azaheterocyclic system, the charge density on carbon atoms *meta* to nitrogen atom is higher than that on other carbon atoms. In 1-aza- and 3-aza-fluoranthene, the charge density on centres C_8 and C_1 , respectively, is highest. Hence, electrophilic attack is most probable on these centres. But experimental results^{17,18} show that centres C_9 is the most suitable place for

electrophilic attack in both the cases and the charge density on this centre is the second highest.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincerest thanks to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support in the form of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (S. K. P). Thanks are also due to Mr. Sunirmal Ghosh for some preliminary work.

References

1. A. DAS GUPTA and N. K. DAS GUPTA, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1976, 54, 3227.
2. N. K. DAS GUPTA and F. W. BIRSS, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1978, 51, 1211, and references therein.
3. R. G. PARR, "Quantum Theory of Molecular Electronic Structure", Benjamin, New York, 1965.
4. R. PARISER and R. G. PARR, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, 21, 466, 767.
5. J. A. POPL, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, 49, 1375.
6. M. J. S. DEWAR and A. J. HARGET, *Proc. Roy. Soc. London, Ser. A*, 1970, 315, 443, 457.
7. M. J. S. DEWAR and N. TRINAJSTIC, *Theor. Chim. Acta*, 1970, 17, 235.
8. K. OHNO, *Theor. Chim. Acta*, 1964, 2, 219.
9. R. PARISER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, 21, 368.
10. J. HINZE and H. H. JAFFE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 540.
11. N. MATAGA and K. NISHIMOTO, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, 13, 140.
12. N. K. DAS GUPTA, A. DAS GUPTA and F. W. BIRSS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, 21, 334.
13. L. SALEM, "Molecular Orbital Theory of Conjugated System", Benjamin, New York, 1966, p. 358.
14. J. MICHL, *Theor. Chim. Acta*, 1969, 15, 315.
15. T. KOOPMANS, *Physica*, 1934, 1, 104.
16. F. W. BIRSS and N. K. DAS GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, 17, 610.
17. N. CAMPBELL and K. F. REID, *J. Chem. Soc. London*, 1958, 4743.
18. C. F. KOELSCH and A. P. STEINHAEUER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 1516.
19. J. MICHL, *Theor. Chim. Acta*, 1969, 20, 66.